

Willkommen zur qualitativen Erhebung zur Nutzung und Weiterentwicklung von persistenten Identifikatoren (PIDs) in Deutschland.

Vielen Dank für Ihr Interesse und Ihre Zeit, sich an dieser Erhebung zu beteiligen.

Im Rahmen des DFG-geförderten Forschungsprojekts "PID Network Deutschland", [506475377](https://www.pidnetwork.de/506475377), zur aktuellen und zukünftigen Nutzung von persistenten Identifikatoren in Deutschland möchten wir mit Ihnen, Akteur*innen aus PID-Registrierungsagenturen, Aggregatoren, Zitationsdatenbanken und Infrastrukturinitiativen, mit dieser Online-Befragung in den Dialog treten. Ziel dieser Befragung ist es, ein fundiertes Bild vom Status quo, zu Ihren bestehenden Bedarfen, Versorgungslücken und den Entwicklungspotenzialen im Umgang mit PIDs zu gewinnen.

Die Teilnahme ist freiwillig.

Die folgenden Fragen dienen als Leitfaden. Freitextfelder ermöglichen Ihnen, Ihre Erfahrungen und Perspektiven ausführlich darzustellen. Es gibt keine „richtigen“ oder „falschen“ Antworten – Ihre individuelle Sichtweise ist für uns von besonderem Wert.

Wir würden uns freuen, wenn wir Ihre Antworten als PDF-Dokument zusammen mit der Auswertung auf [Zenodo.org](https://zenodo.org) veröffentlichen dürften.

Keine Teilnahme

Zur Veröffentlichung:

Zustimmung

Keine Zustimmung

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Für Rückfragen stehe ich, Andreas Czerniak (andreas.czerniak@uni-bielefeld.de), Ihnen selbstverständlich jederzeit zur Verfügung. Darüber hinaus unterstützen wir, das PID-Network Projekt-Team (info.pidnetwork@listserv.dfn.de), Sie gerne bei sämtlichen Fragen im Zusammenhang mit PIDs – sowohl im nationalen als auch im internationalen Kontext.

Herzlichen Dank!

1. Status quo und Nutzung

Status quo und Nutzung

Eine Leitfrage in diesem Abschnitt könnte sein:

- Wie wird Ihre Infrastruktur bzw. Ihr Dienst aktuell genutzt, und welche typischen Nutzungsszenarien oder Anwendungsfälle lassen sich dabei identifizieren?

Status quo and usage

How is your infrastructure or service currently being used, and what typical usage scenarios or use cases can be identified?

The current status of KonsortSWD PID registration service [i]. is a fully tested prototype. It was piloted, and tests were implemented in collaboration with multiple research data centers (RDCs), including GESIS, DZHW, DIW, and Qualiservice. The service enables the registration of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for dataset elements, such as variables, survey questions, and qualitative data segments (e.g., audio/video segments, text excerpts, and image areas), extending beyond the traditional dataset or study level.

- Fully Tested Prototype:

As of 2025, the service has been developed into a fully tested prototype [ii] [iii] and evaluated by several RDCs. The infrastructure features a robust metadata schema and a bulk PID registration process facilitated by JSON submissions.

A test environment (provided by GWDG) supports real-time registration of thousands of PIDs [iv], enabling iterative testing and alignment between local metadata systems and the central PID infrastructure

- **RDC Use Cases:**

GESIS: Registered hundreds of variable-level test PIDs. The usage of the PID at this level can offer researchers a stable citation method and machine-actionable metadata to link variables with associated instruments and concepts.

Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies (DZHW) (implemented in 2024) [v]: Implemented tests PIDs for variables within their metadata system (FDZ-DZHW-MDM), with over 32,000 variables available, and assigned a landing page structure for each version.

German Socio-Economic Panel (SOEP), located at the German Institute for Economic Research (DIW) (implemented in 2023) [vi]: Tested metadata completeness, mapping, and landing page generation for its SOEP study, validating its ability to register variables with test PIDs via the PID service.

Qualiservice at University of Bremen [vii]: Focused on registering non-rectangular data elements (e.g., interview excerpts, audiovisual segments), providing granularity for qualitative data through metadata structures compatible with Schema.org and DDI standards.

- Typical Usage Scenarios and Benefits:

Fine-Grained Citation and Discovery:

Researchers can identify and cite individual variables or fragments within large datasets (e.g., a specific interview quote, a video segment, or a questionnaire item), thereby increasing the precision of citations and the reproducibility of results [viii].

Linking Related Entities:

The infrastructure supports interlinking across datasets, questions, answers, and metadata using controlled vocabularies and relation types (e.g., IsPartOf, IsVersionOf) [ix], helping to build semantic connections across studies and survey waves.

Qualitative Data Support:

The system includes specific metadata for audio, video, and image segments, including timestamps and coordinates. This is crucial for qualitative research, as it enables the citation and reuse of non-coded material at the segment level.

Automated Metadata Handling and FAIR Compliance:

By enabling bulk PID registration via JSON [x], the infrastructure promotes machine-actionable FAIR metadata practices, reducing manual documentation.

2. Infrastruktur und Dienste

Einige Leitfragen in diesem Abschnitt können sein:

- Welche wissenschaftlichen Infrastrukturen und Dienste sind für den Betrieb und die Weiterentwicklung hinsichtlich PIDs für Ihren Dienst aus Ihrer Sicht besonders relevant?

- Für welche externen Dienste oder Infrastrukturen stellt Ihr Dienst derzeit wesentliche Funktionalitäten oder Schnittstellen bereit, und in welcher Form geschieht dies? Welche Rolle spielen hierbei PIDs?
- Nutzen Sie PIDs für den Betrieb Ihres Dienstes?
- ● In your opinion, which scientific infrastructures and services are particularly relevant for the operation and further development of PIDs for your service here?

Cross-Consortia Applicability in NFDI:

- The PID service is designed as a domain-agnostic infrastructure, developed initially within KonsortSWD, but applicable across all NFDI consortia. Its metadata schema currently supports registration of dataset elements such as variables, survey questions, and qualitative data files or segments.
- Extending the schema [xi] to accommodate other types of dataset elements would require new feature development, including updates to the metadata model and registration logic. Such efforts would depend on continued funding and cross-consortia collaboration.
- ● For which external services or infrastructures does your service currently provide essential functionalities or interfaces, and in what form does this take place? What role do PIDs play in this?
- The PID registration service supports integration with external PID infrastructures such as DataCite and the ePIC Handle system. This ensures interoperability with existing NFDI services and global PID ecosystems.
- PIDs play a crucial role in enabling the standardized identification of data fragments, including media segments, text excerpts, and qualitative data segments. Potentially, if there is a service upgrade, it can register any dataset element from any domain that requires PIDs at a lower level of data granularity.
- ● Do you use PIDs for the operation of your service?
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- Yes. The primary function of the service is to assign PIDs to dataset elements at a granular level.
- Additionally, the service uses existing PIDs—typically DOIs—to identify the parent objects (e.g., datasets, studies, or surveys) from which the registered elements

originate. This ensures hierarchical consistency in PID resolution and allows linking between the element-level PID and its broader research context.

3. Bedarfe und Wünsche

Einige Leitfragen in diesem Abschnitt können sein:

- Welche konkreten Entwicklungen oder Veränderungen wären aus Ihrer Sicht wünschenswert, um das Potenzial von PIDs besser auszuschöpfen?
 - Welche strukturellen, technischen oder politischen Maßnahmen wären notwendig, um den Ausbau von PID-Infrastrukturen in Deutschland gezielt zu fördern?
- In your opinion, what specific developments or changes would be desirable in order to better exploit the potential of PIDs?
- Advance the current fully tested prototype into a productive mode, assign productive prefixes for use case partners, provide scripts to extract use cases metadata as a data ingestion layer, including automatically generating the PID proposal (which is required).
- What structural, technical, or political measures would be necessary to specifically promote the expansion of PID infrastructures in Germany?
- Integrate PID services into existing national infrastructures (e.g., NFDI, DFG-funded services, libraries) as core components.
 - Support cross-consortia collaboration to share schema extensions, metadata mappings, and best practices for assigning PIDs at different levels of granularity.
 - It would have been extremely helpful to have a tool that compares and highlights differences between metadata fields across various metadata schemas.
- Technical Measures:
- Fund the development and maintenance of reusable tools, APIs, and metadata mappers that allow comparison of metadata schemas for datasets and their elements across domains.

- Provide stable and scalable test and production environments for PID registration workflows, including automated validation, bulk processing, and integration with metadata repositories.
- Support technical implementation of landing pages, versioning strategies, and machine-actionable metadata, especially for complex data types (e.g., qualitative, geospatial, audiovisual).

Political Measures:

- Include mandatory PID adoption policies for publicly funded research projects and data repositories, including requirements for granular PIDs where appropriate (e.g., variables, samples, fragments).
- Require assessment of those policies on the EU level, such as EOSC-compliant Persistent Identifier (PID) policies, using, for example, the FAIRCORE4EOSC Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT).^[xii]
- Ensure long-term funding models for PID services, especially for those supporting element-level identification, which are more resource-intensive than traditional dataset-level DOIs. Important to mention that EOSC already advocates for PID on a lower granularity level ^[xiii]

4. Empfehlungen

Eine Leitfrage in diesem Abschnitt kann sein:

- Welche Akteure (z. B. Forschungsinfrastrukturen, Fachgesellschaften/-Communities, Förderorganisationen, Bibliotheken) sehen Sie in der Verantwortung, um eine effektivere Nutzung von PIDs zu ermöglichen und welche Aufgaben sollten diese jeweils übernehmen?
 - Welche ergänzenden Aspekte halten Sie für relevant und welche Empfehlungen würden Sie uns im Hinblick auf deren Berücksichtigung geben?
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- Which actors (e.g., research infrastructures, professional associations/communities, funding organizations, libraries) do you consider responsible for enabling more effective use of PIDs, and what tasks should each of them take on?
 - What additional aspects do you consider relevant, and what recommendations would you give us with regard to taking them into account?

- Cross-domain metadata comparability: Tools that help compare metadata schemas across disciplines (e.g., a “metadata marketplace”) would facilitate alignment and reuse of PID services beyond individual domains.
- Sustainability planning. Ensure that PID infrastructures are supported by robust governance models and long-term funding strategies to prevent fragmentation and service discontinuity.
- Support for non-rectangular data types (e.g., qualitative excerpts, images, audio) should be recognized as a key requirement in future PID developments, especially to meet the needs of disciplines outside of the traditional quantitative domains.
- User-focused tooling and automation. Simplifying PID registration, metadata preparation, and integration into existing data systems will drive wider adoption.

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